

A Study of the Outcomes of a Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) 7-Day Healing Camp for Health & Wellness Conducted at the YPV Ashram, Sri Ramana Trust in December 2023

Vishakha Karnani¹, Venkata Satyanarayana Nanduri²

¹Senior Arhat Trainer, YPV Level 6 Healer, Indore, MP

²Consultant, Research & Publications, YPV Ashram, Sri Ramana Trust, Thally-635118, Tamil Nadu

ABSTRACT

Introduction: The integrated and holistic healing protocols of the Yoga Prana vidya (YPV) system have been making significant contributions to people as complementary and alternative therapies to the various mainstream healthcare systems. YPV healing camps are conducted by Competent YPV healers to raise the awareness of people on the need to learn and practice healthy lifestyles for the cure and prevention of diseases. This paper presents the outcomes of one such Health & Wellness camp conducted by a team of 8 YPV healers for a week in December 2023.

Method: This is an interventional study with data collected from 27 patients who participated in the camp. Data was collected on selected health parameters before and after the camp ended to know the improvements the patients experienced in this one-week camp.

Results: The mean body weight and BMI (Body mass Index) reduced by 1.88 % and 1.66% respectively. Those with diabetes and BP became normal. Patients who had physical pain, mobility, and flexibility issues were greatly relieved and were able to walk normally. Cases of constipation, hypothyroidism, psoriasis, varicose veins, and acne were resolved to return to normal condition. An alcoholic case was successfully de-addicted after 3 days of healing treatment. Improvements were noticed in patients with eye/vision problems. Those who had mental and emotional issues were also found to be calm and peaceful by the end of the camp.

Conclusions: It is observed that the patients in this YPV healing camp experienced satisfactory improvements in their health and wellness issues. The team of healers did a dedicated service helping and treating the patients holistically with a combination of exercises, rhythmic breathing protocols, the right diet, and meditations. The patients appreciated and practiced the lifestyle changes needed based on the principles of YPV energy healing system protocols. There is great scope to conduct more such camps in rural and semi-urban areas to disseminate this knowledge to the general population.

KEYWORDS: Health & Wellness camps, Yoga Prana Vidya®, YPV®

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YPV Healing Camps

All matter in the universe is fundamentally transformed from Energy which exists universally in abundance. It has been observed that there is an energy body surrounding the physical body of living beings such as humans and animals. YPV system of healing recognises and utilises this energy principle, and focuses on utilizing the subtle energy (or Prana) to treat and alleviate a large number of ailments and discomforts ranging from physical, emotional, mental, and over weight and facial skin stresses. Recorded evidence of the

effectiveness of YPV system of healing is available in over 100 published research papers. Documented evidence is also available showing successful outcomes of some YPV healing camps conducted previously [1] [2] [3] [4] [5]. As an integrated and holistic system, YPV has been found helpful as complementary medicine and also as an alternative medicine in cases where there are no proven treatments available in mainstream medicine [6 -16].

The YPV Ashram has an environment conducive to health and wellness camps and is a proven retreat for sick people to

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recover within days of participating in a camp. This paper presents the outcomes of one such camp conducted at the YPV Ashram for a week during December 2023.

Camp details

This camp was organized and conducted under the guidance of a Senior YPV and Arhat trainer and level 6 healer. This one-week Healing camp was announced 2 months in advance of the scheduled dates and the team of healers spread the word around amongst the patients and others whom they could reach. The message was posted in all the groups of various healers and in some cases, people themselves approached, whereas in others they were told about the benefits one could get by attending such a healing camp. Regular follow-ups were done explaining to them the benefits and helping them plan to reach the healing camp. The Healing Camp, which was a one-week fully residential programme, was conducted at the YPV Ashram of Sri Ramana Trust situated near a village called Thally in Tamil Nadu from 9th to 15th December 2023.

Patients' profile

Patients came from several parts of the country seeking YPV healing intervention in the YPV Ashram premises to find solutions to their nagging health and fitness issues. There were a total of 27 participants from different parts of India (Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Gujarat, Maharashtra and Karnataka). Among the 27 total number of participants, there were 19 adult females, 7 adult males, and 1 Male child. The age group ranged from 8 years to 75 years. They arrived on 8th December and the integrated YPV healing programme was conducted for them from 9th to 15th December (1 week).

YPV Intervention

The objective of the healing camp was to apply YPV healing protocols to heal each patient in group, and also individually, to improve their well-being physically, emotionally, and mentally. For this camp-based healing intervention, the patients were asked to bring their recent medical reports for assessment and to work out appropriate strategies for healing. For psychological and other mental health related ailments,

the healers collected the necessary information from each patient before the camp started. It is well known that excessive body weight and obesity cause several illnesses. Therefore their body weight and BMI were recorded at their entry to the programme, and again after the last day of camp. In respect of those having blood sugar and BP issues, these parameters were checked at entry, exit, and also in between. The schedule for this holistic healing camp included exercising twice a day (morning and evening), walking (at least twice a day), breathing exercises including rhythmic yogic breathing (at least twice a day), forgiveness sadhana (at least once daily) and doing the morning sadhana (meditation with self-healing) after the exercise.

Before the morning schedule of exercising and sadhana, the participants were offered no-milk special tea (lemon grass and black pepper, ginger) and Sat-isabgol to detox. After the morning Sadhana, breakfast was provided with fruits and fresh and tender coconut water.

Subsequently, a divine group healing session of 15 minutes duration was conducted for them, followed by healing with the laying down of crystal pebbles individually on the patients during which the "Om shanti" mantra was played in the background. After this, individual healing was given to each patient on 3 levels (first by a YPV associate certified healer, then by a YPV level 5 healer, and finally by YPV level 6 healers) thereby ensuring a thorough healing given daily.

The lunch included a simple, unsalted balanced vegetarian meal. After lunch they were asked to rest for a couple of hours before they returned in the evening for exercise, breathing, and walking followed by evening tea and some light snacks different on each day (roasted peanuts, puffed rice, boiled corn, a small portion of sweet potato, etc.).

After the tea break, there was a book study session, where different topics such as forgiveness, and how healing occurs on emotional and mental levels were discussed. The day would end with a 15-minute forgiveness sadhana after which they dispersed for dinner and a good night's sleep.

The camp was headed by a Senior YPV and Arhat trainer and level 6 healer who led a team of healers as stated in Table 1 consisting of 8 healers who served the patients in the camp.

Table 1: Team of healers

YPV Healer code name	YPV competency level
VK	Level 6 Healer
UK	Level 5 Healer
MM	Level 5 Healer
PM	Level 5 Healer
KS	Associate Certified Healer
KP	Associate Certified Healer
SD	Healer Development Program Level 1 (HDPL1) Healer
NP	HDPL1 Healer

In addition to the above stated 8 healers, the Founder of YPV System, who is the senior most YPV healer, also conducted

individual healing sessions for each participant on all days of the camp to ensure powerful healing intervention.

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The health issues reported by each patient for healing are stated in Table 2.

Table 2: Health issues reported by patients

Patient	Gender	Age	Presenting Health issues
1	F	70	Blood glucose level Above 200, despite insulin use
2	F	63	history of stroke and partial paralysis. Low Mobility and flexibility
3	F	45	Severe knee pain and high blood sugar levels.
4	M	60	increased blood sugar level, enlarged prostate gland, constipation issues and disturbed sleep.
5	F	40	Hyperthyroidism
6	M	60	Psoriasis
7	F	54	stressed after cancer treatment, varicose veins. She could not walk properly.
8	F	30	Lupus patient of 6 years, swollen legs, unable to walk, Nausea, vomiting
9	M	27	Stressed and depressed due to joblessness, back pain
10	F	54	Cervical spondylosis
11	F	53	Overweight, Knee pain, high BP, sugar,
12	F	23	Acne
13	F	42	she has been in depression since years
14	F	69	neck spondylosis, depression, diabetic, BP
15	F	57	Muscle weakness, swelling all over the body,
16	M	67	BP high, sugar high, floaters and retina problem in eyes, difficulty in walking due to knee and foot pain
17	F	75	swelling and pus in the right collar bone, frozen shoulder, pyorrhea
18	F	48	high blood sugar
19	F	32	Anger, ego, lack of peace, Lower back pain,
20	M	35	acidity, severe constipation, lower back pain, stress, mood swings, alcohol addiction,
21	F	53	nagging muscle pain in the thighs and around the elbow area.
22	F	37	Fear and lack of peace
23	M	61	Uncontrolled diabetes over 25 years
24	F	51	constipation and severe backpain
25	F	36	diabetic with insulin use, BP, swelling in abdomen
26	M	25	twisted ankle and torn ligament due to fall, shoulder and neck pain due to work posture,
27	M	8	Cylindrical eye power in both eyes

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The categories of Illnesses and number of cases reported are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3: Main categories and number of cases

S.No	Illness	No. of cases
1	Diabetes	8
2	BP/Hyper tension	4
3	Constipation	2
4	Hypothyroidism	1
5	Psoriasis	1
6	Varicose veins	1
7	Acne	1
8	Physical pain/Mobility/flexibility	15
9	Alcoholism	1
10	Mental and emotional issues	4
11	Eye/Vision problems	2

RESULTS

Quantitative results:

1. Body weight (Kg): The mean value of body weight of the adult 26 participants at entry to the camp was 66.89, and 65.63 at the end of the camp, showing a reduction of 1.88%.
2. Body Mass Index (BMI): The BMI of 26 participants showed a reduction of 1.66% at the end of the camp.

Qualitative results:

1. Blood glucose level

In the case of six Type 2 diabetes patients, blood glucose levels reduced to normal. Two cases of patients with insulin use experienced lower glucose levels, and their insulin dosage was reduced by 40 % by medical advice.

2. BP

BP normalised for all 4 patients. One of them was advised to discontinue medication upon medical advice.

3. Constipation

The two patients who earlier reported issues of constipation found complete relief. Peaceful sleep ensued as a result.

4. The hypothyroidism patient found that his TSH levels reduced to normal.

5. Psoriasis of the patient was completely healed.

6. Varicose vein issue of the patient was resolved. The patient walked confidently without stress.

7. The patient with acne problem felt good and relieved.

8. Physical pain, mobility, flexibility:

All 15 patients who had earlier reported various bouts of pain experienced a substantial reduction in pain with increased flexibility and mobility. It was agreed by all patients that their weight reduction in the camp enabled improvements in mobility.

9. Alcoholism:

An Alcoholic with acidity and lower back pain reported that within 3 days of healing, acidity and lower back pain disappeared. The urge for alcohol disappeared, and

miraculous changes have taken place through attending this camp.

10. Mental and emotional issues:

All 4 patients who complained earlier about their mental and emotional issues achieved inner peace and came out of fear. Many positive changes in thinking and behaviour have taken place. The depression was eliminated. Anger and ego were reduced substantially. One of them achieved a peaceful state of mind, and she felt so good that she extended her stay in the Ashram by 2 more weeks to attend the Arhat Yoga program.

11. Eye/vision problems

One patient's Cylindrical Eye power issue was reduced by 0.25. The other patient's Retina problem in the eye and floaters were reduced by 50%.

DISCUSSION

It is observed that the patients in this YPV healing camp experienced satisfactory improvements in their health and wellness issues. The most common ailments are pain, diabetes, and hypertension caused by a lack of physical activity and self-care. The team of dedicated YPV healers ensured that the patient's health concerns were addressed effectively by compassionate counselling and understanding of their needs. The results obtained through this camp compare well with previously conducted YPV healing camps reported [1] [2] [3] [4] [5].

CONCLUSIONS

Yoga Prana Vidya healing camps have been very successfully conducted for awareness of self-care and lifestyle modifications needed to improve the health and wellness of the general population. Through these camps, people of all ages have been learning proven and safe methods of preventive care as well. These camps have also helped the participants to appreciate the need and learn, become healers, and practice basic levels of YPV energy healing techniques. The Great Vision of the YPV system promotes the aim to have

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at least one YPV healer in every family to maintain the health and wellness of its members.

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